

A Study On Rearing And Grainage Performance Of *Antheraea Assamensis* Helfer. In Assam

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Muga silkworm, *Antheraea assamensis*, Helfer., is the producer of golden yellow luster with durability and fine texture which is indigenous to the Brahmaputra valley of Assam. Five accessions of Muga silkworm, *Antheraea assamensis*, Helfer., were collected from different Muga growing areas of Assam, and assigned with accession numbers (AC-1 to AC-5). Rearing and grainage performance were studied under natural conditions for 2 years and analysed. Wide range of variability was observed among the populations in terms of rearing and grainage performance. AC-4 was considered as the best performer in both rearing and grainage performance with larval weight 14.5g, ERR 63.5%, Cocoon weight 4.89g in male and 7.26g in female, Shell weight 0.67g, Fecundity 162 nos.. AC-2 and AC-5 also exhibited superiority in rearing and grainage performance, which may be utilized for yield of hybrids.

Keywords: *Antheraea assamensis*, accessions, rearing performance, grainage performance, morphological characterization